

**THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE ENTERPRISE ECONOMY
DEPENDS ON THE BALANCED AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT
OF ITS REGIONS**

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Abstract: *The economic development of any enterprise depends on the balanced and sustainable development of its territories.*

Key words: *Value addition, marketing, enterprises, industry, development of networks, diversification and localization.*

In the sustainable development of regions and their territories, the importance of industrial sectors is high. Because industrial sectors, in addition to ensuring the rate of economic growth, create a basis for increasing the competitiveness of the economy by stimulating the diversification and localization of production. Processing of all raw materials mined in the industrial sector, created in production, and due to the production of various products from them, diversification processes will be improved. In the world experience, the practice of developed countries with high growth rates shows that their success was mainly due to structural changes in industrial sectors, in particular, processing industries.

The difference between the industry and other sectors is that it creates a high level of added value. Added value is the sequence of the production process of creating a specific type of product, processing it, conducting marketing activities, and finally delivering it to consumption.

The formation and development or change in the level of innovative activity of enterprises occurs as a result of the influence of certain factors. During the

objective and comprehensive research of the management of innovative activities of the enterprise, the problem of identifying and systematizing the factors affecting it will be urgent and insufficiently developed.

By the factor of innovative activity, we understand the conditions, reasons and indicators that affect the speed and description of the innovative growth of the enterprise. In this case, the innovative process takes place as a result of the interaction of many factors.

The analysis of scientific literature shows that the classification of factors affecting innovative activity was not developed at the same time. Many authors have focused their attention on the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise. T.G. In her work, Filosofova noted the following factors that hinder innovation in industrial enterprises:

- lack of economic - financial resources, low funding from the state, high costs for innovation promotion, high level of economic risk, long period of innovation returns;

- production - lack of qualified personnel, lack of necessary information about new technologies, sales markets, inability of the organization to quickly adopt innovations, lack of cooperation with other organizations, enterprises and scientific organizations, or absence;

- other factors - low price demand by consumers for innovative products, lack of sufficient legal and regulatory frameworks and regulation in innovative activities, insufficient stimulation of innovative activities by the state, poorly developed innovative infrastructure, lack of development in the technology market .

A.A. Bovin cites and analyzes the following factors influencing the innovation environment of the organization:

- social infrastructure (employees' access to services in educational, medical and cultural facilities);

- communication field (possibility of using communication, information resources);
- natural - geographical conditions (availability of transport, material and technical, energy, fuel and raw materials resources);

- technological and scientific-technical field (availability of the development market, availability of scientific-research institutes, etc.);

- economic and financial sphere (state support of innovative activities at the national and regional level, presence of investors interested in innovative developments);

- political-legal sphere (existence of national, regional plans and programs in the legal regulation of the innovative and scientific-technical sphere);

- strategic coverage of business (speed of innovation in a certain segment of the market);

- labor market.

In our opinion, the presented classifications cover only a small part of the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise. It should be noted that the factors that directly affect innovative activity have not been identified in the scientific literature.

The main goal of our research is to determine the impact of the activities of industrial enterprises on the efficiency of the regional economy based on the classification of factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise. In our opinion, it is appropriate to classify the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise according to a number of signs. As a result of the conducted research, the following classification signs of the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise can be proposed according to the level of management.

According to the sources of origin, factors are divided into natural-climatic, social, financial-economic, industrial-technological, scientific-technical and organizational-management groups.

Natural and climatic factors have a great influence on the results of innovative activities of industrial enterprises. The availability of water supply, favorable climate, working conditions, and large sources of fuel and raw materials greatly contribute to the development of innovative activities of industrial enterprises located in the region and the growth of innovative activities.

Complexity of natural and climatic conditions, lack of labor force, production forces, low level of transport development, on the contrary, hindering the development of innovative activity of the enterprise, together with a huge amount of money for the solution of the above-mentioned problems, which negatively affect the level of innovative activity of the enterprise ' requires.

Social factors include the demographic situation, the level of social tension, the living conditions of workers, health care at the enterprise, the organization of sports and cultural activities, the general cultural and educational level of personnel, and others. These serve to ensure the effective and full use of the company's production resources, corporate development and formation of human capital.

Financial and economic factors determine the availability of funds, raw materials, and the level of opportunities to attract additional funds. Researching the financial and economic factors of innovative activity, first of all, provides an opportunity to research the financial capabilities of the enterprise in the innovative development, to develop in advance the direction of the development of the innovative strategy in the current and future financial situation of the company.

Industrial-technological factors determine the effective and full use of the company's production resources and technologies.

The transfer of ITTKI to scientific and technical factors covers the existence of intellectual property.

The analysis of organizational and management factors helps to determine the level of development of the innovation infrastructure, effective innovation

management, marketing strategy in the implementation of innovations, the organization of innovation financing, and the suitability of the organizational structure to the tasks of innovative activity.

In our opinion, it is necessary to classify the factors affecting innovative activity according to the level of management.

When classifying the factors affecting the innovative activity of the enterprise according to the level of management, the factors that directly or indirectly affect the enterprise, as well as the impact of changing the level of its innovative activity and the factors that the enterprise cannot influence can be noted.

Based on the above, the classification of innovative activity factors according to the level of management is the most important in considering the issues of expanding and evaluating the level of innovative activity of the enterprise.

Indirectly controlled factors - these are the results of the impact on the innovative activity of the enterprise, related to the way management decisions are made, the influence of external factors.

In conclusion, the influence of indirectly controlled factors on the development of the innovative activity of the enterprise is related to the management decisions of financial institutions that influence innovative projects, the state policy in the field of innovation and the industrial systems of those interested in the promotion of innovation (banking sector, state investors, etc.).

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